

QUIZ**LAST NAME: DRAMMEH****FIRST NAME: SAIBO****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Turabian (footnotes)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is plagiarism?

- When a writer uses a source of information without given credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- Writing without proper citation.
- Writing an academic paper with many grammatical errors.
- Plagiarism is when a writer fails to indicate his identity and source of information.

2. What is the difference between citation and paraphrasing?

- Citation is writing in the present tense, whilst paraphrasing is writing in the past tense.

¹ Cleenwerk, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, Second Edition. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 4.

- Citation is when using the exact words of an author by placing them between quotation marks. Paraphrasing means rephrasing the original text in your own words.²**
- Citation is quoting in the middle of a paragraph, whilst paraphrasing means quoting at the end of a paragraph.
- Citation indicates the date and author of an information, and paraphrasing indicates the source of the information without date.

3. **Explain one major difference between American and British Style**

- Apartment in British English means flat in American English.
- American Style places punctuations inside quotation marks, whilst British Style places punctuations outside quotation marks.³**
- In American Style all nouns are written in capital letters and in British Style not.
- American Style uses in-text citations and British Style uses bibliography.

4. **Describe the difference between subjective and personal writing**

- Subjective writing is when you are writing about a subject and personal writing is when you are writing about yourself.
- Subjective writing is when writing a story from the perspective of the subject and personal writing is when writing about yourself.
- Subjective writing is when writing biography or news stories and personal writing is when writing friendly letters or autobiography.⁴**

² Ibid., 5

³ Ibid., 27

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, (Wilmington, WI: Great Source Education Group Inc., 1999), 144-175.

- Subjective writing is usually done by a group of people and personal writing is done by a single person.

5. **Explain briefly what proofreading is**

- Proofreading is proving your reading skills.
- Proofreading is when a writer reads out his story loud to a public.
- Proofreading is the process of becoming a professional writer.
- Proofreading is when a writer controls the finish writing product before final publication.⁵**

6. **Research can simply be defined as ...**

- Searching for facts in the internet.
- Systematic gathering of information or data and presenting it with the best credible evidence available to everyone.⁶**
- Professional collection of guidelines perfectly designed for researchers.
- Answering a specific question for others to know the right answer.

7. **What is a working hypothesis and what is a claim?**

- Research writing begins with a question which is the hypothesis and the answer is the claim.
- Hypothesis is the topic you are writing about and the claim is the question you want your readers to answer.

⁵ Ibid., 5

⁶ Turabian, Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Eighth Edition. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

- The writing process is the hypothesis and the claim is the conclusion.
- Researchers usually begin their writing project with a topic asking a question worth answering and answering this specific question for others to understand by providing reliable evidence to substantiate the facts is your working hypothesis. Building your arguments around answers to readers' questions by providing solid reasons based on reliable evidence turns your working hypothesis into a claim.** ⁷

8. **What are the common errors in research papers?**

- The conclusions are longer than the introductions.
- Short introductions and conclusions.
- Grammatical errors, wrong spellings as well as inaccurate words or phrases.** ⁸
- Confusing major and academic papers.

9. **Point out one main difference between Harvard and Oxford rule of styles**

- Harvard Rule of Style is American, whilst Oxford Rule of Style is British
- Harvard Rule of Style uses in-text citations and reference list or bibliography at the end of the document, whilst Oxford Rule of Style uses footnotes to place references at the end of each page and a reference list at the end of the document.** ⁹

⁷ Ibid., 17-23

⁸ Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 3.

⁹ Ibid., 69-124

- Harvard Rule of Style is reviewed every two years, whilst Oxford Rule of Style is reviewed every year.
- Harvard Rule of Style is for professional writers and Oxford Rule of Style is for students.

10. How many countries are currently Member States of the European Union?

- 25 Member States.
- 20 Member States.
- 30 Member States.
- 28 Member States.**¹⁰

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Seventh Edition, 2011.

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